

The Thornhill Map: A Case Study of Inspiration on the Academic and Professional Development of Two South African Researchers

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Abstract: Nina Thornhill's work has influenced research across the world. In this contribution, we show how her academic presence has influenced our own academic and professional development. To visualize influence, we make use of a connectivity map (as popularized by Nina Thornhill in the context of process monitoring) to show the propagation of ideas and the connection of people – the Thornhill map. Although we have never met Nina, we have been inspired by her work, and we wish her much joy and peaceful reflection in her retirement.

Keywords: Causality; Propagation paths

1 INTRODUCTION

On the occasion of Nina Thornhill's retirement, we would like to describe how Nina's work has inspired our own academic and professional development, as well as thank her for this inspiration.

Although we have never met Nina, her academic presence has affected our careers in two distinct ways. Firstly, Nina's publications on connectivity/causality; control performance/faults; and process simulation inspired the topics and methodologies of several research projects we have been involved in. Secondly, we were very fortunate to start collaborating with Margret Bauer, whose promotor for her doctoral studies was Nina.

In this contribution, we demonstrate and discuss the influence of Nina Thornhill's work in our case by means of a connectivity map.

2 BACKGROUND

Some background on the authors of this contribution is required to provide context to the subsequent connectivity map.

Lidia is a first-generation university graduate from Stellenbosch University. After completing her Bachelor's in Chemical Engineering degree and PhD in Extractive Metallurgical Engineering, she started as a lecturer at the Department of Process Engineering at Stellenbosch University (South Africa) in January 2012. One of her first tasks as a new academic was to define a number of undergraduate research projects for final-year Chemical Engineering graduates. Her research up to that point had mainly been concerned with data-driven fault detection. The question of data-driven root cause analysis (for example, through data-driven causality methods [1]) had piqued her interest. This became the inspiration for one of the

undergraduate research projects, undertaken by Brian Lindner in 2012.

Brian continued with Master's (2015) and PhD (2019) research projects in the field of data-driven causality, and is currently employed as a data scientist at Stone Three Digital, developing data analytical tools (including causality analysis, nonlinearity index and spectral envelope oscillation detection) as well as providing remote process monitoring services to industrial clients. Margret Bauer, a former student of Nina, came on board as a co-supervisor for Brian's PhD. Through Margret, Brian collaborated with Moncef Cioua and Matthieu Lucke (both from ABB) during his PhD research.

What started out as an interesting research question for an undergraduate student turned into inspiration for academic and professional development.

3 METHODOLOGY

To illustrate the influence of Nina's work, we use a connectivity map (as used extensively by Nina and co-authors for visualizing process connectivity, causality and propagation paths of process disturbances). In our connectivity map, it is not faults that are propagating across space and time, but ideas and inspiration.

The nodes in the connectivity map represent research artefacts: publications, student theses and monitoring tools. Our goal was not to be exhaustive in representing these research artefacts, but to highlight key contributions and outcomes. To add context and additional opportunities for pattern discovery, the nodes are annotated by different features: artefact type, contributing authors/supervisors, reference numbers, publication year, as well as coded according to a specific theme (connectivity/causality; control performance/faults; process simulation).

The edges in the connectivity map represent direction of influence/inspiration. Again, our goal was not to be

exhaustive in adding edges between all publications cited, but to show key flows of inspiration from one artefact to another.

The data format for the connectivity map generation included the following fields:

Table 1: Fields for connectivity map input data, with examples

Field	Description	Example
Short hand	Short description of output for quick identification purposes	Propagation path
Reference	Numbered citation, where the number will be used in the node annotation for a specific node	[1] Bauer, M., Thornhill, N.F., A practical method for identifying the propagation path of plant-wide disturbances, Journal of Process Control, Volume 18, Issues 7–8, 2008, Pages 707-719.
Year	Year of output	2008
Output number	Node number	1
Type of output	Type of output: Publication, student thesis or monitoring tool	Publication
Topic of output	Main theme: C = connectivity/causality; P = control performance/faults; S = process simulation	C
Authors	For the purpose of this contribution, the authors/contributors of interest were Nina Thornhill, Margret Bauer, Brian Lindner and Lidia Auret	Margret, Nina
From output	Nodes connecting to this output	(none in this case)

A selection of 25 outputs (see [1 – 25] in the reference list) was made to represent key influencing publications and resulting outputs, and these outputs were captured in the data format provided in Table 1.

Python code was written to automatically construct a connectivity map based on the input data in the format described in Table 1 (one row for each output). The code is available on request – please email the corresponding author.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The resulting connectivity map, showing the propagation of ideas and connection of people, can be seen in Figure 1 (we would like to think of this visualization as the Thornhill map).

The key connectivity papers by Nina that stands at the root of the Thornhill map [1, 2] describe approaches for identifying propagation paths/cause-effect analysis of plant-wide disturbances. This inspired Brian’s undergraduate project

[12], as well as through propagation Brian’s Master’s and PhD projects [11, 12]. Further idea propagation can be seen in the monitoring tools [24, 25] for industrial application that have been developed by Brian for the purpose of oscillation diagnosis and causality map generation.

While Brian’s causality work has focussed mostly on correlation methods, Granger causality and transfer entropy, a paper co-authored by Nina which touched on Bayesian networks for cause-effect analysis [6] influenced another student supervised by Lidia [22].

Another paper [3] by Nina inspired the use of realistic simulation in the assessment of control, fault diagnosis and causality techniques in work by Brian [13, 14, 18] and other students supervised by Lidia [22, 23].

Publications by Nina on control performance monitoring [8] and control fault simulation (specifically, valve stiction) [4] inspired work by a student supervised by Lidia [23] who created a high-fidelity simulation of a high pressure base metal leaching process, incorporating a library of realistic process faults and disturbances, assessing control performance in the presence of such faults.

A notable presence and catalyst in this Thornhill map is Margret Bauer. During Brian’s undergraduate and Master’s projects, the papers written by Margret and Nina provided much inspiration. Some years later in 2016, Lidia attended the annual general meeting of the South African Council for Automation and Control (SACAC). Margret Bauer, then an Associate Professor at University Witwatersrand and Principal Scientist at ABB Corporate Research, was the guest speaker (on topics of Industrie 4.0 and low-cost sensing). Lidia was very excited to meet this wonderful researcher and inspiration for Brian’s projects. Not only was Margret’s talk very interesting, Margret herself was very friendly and approachable. After some discussion, Margret agreed to come on board as a co-supervisor for Brian’s PhD. Margret not only contributed great ideas, steely discipline in paper-writing (as evidenced in [14, 15, 17, 18, 19] but also connections to other research opportunities [8, 9, 16] and research exchange opportunities for Brian to ABB (where he met Moncef and Matthieu).

5 CONCLUSIONS

Overall, the Thornhill map in Figure 1 gives a brief overview of a specific case study on the propagation of ideas and connection of people inspired by some of Nina’s work. We have been inspired by her work and wish her the best in her retirement.

Fig. 1. Connectivity map showing influence of Nina Thornhill's work on selected outputs by the authors of this paper. Nodes indicate publications (squares), student theses (pentagons) and monitoring tools (circles). Node edge colours represent authors / contributors: Nina (blue), Margret (red), Brian (orange), Lidia (green). Node annotations indicate references (bracketed numbers), year of publication, and overall theme (C = connectivity/causality; P = control performance/control system faults; S = realistic process simulation). Edges represent inspiration from one output to another. We are happy to share the code used to generate this connectivity map – please email the corresponding author.

6 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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